

Review Article

Overcoming the Problems of Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria: The Ways Forward

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Abstract

The level of agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria is indeed low. This is attributed to the fact that many of our farmers and processors are still used to the traditional methods of practicing agriculture thereby not giving attention to the creation of mechanical means which has the added advantage of boosting their farm produce and products. This paper through secondary source of information had identified several areas where we went wrong and as a result of this, proffered several ways forward in overcoming the problems of agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria.

Keywords: overcoming, mechanization, Nigeria, produce, farmers, products

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Introduction

Nigerian Agricultural Sector

According to Kasali (2018), the agricultural sector of Nigeria is classified into four subsectors namely, crops, livestock, fisheries and forestry subsectors. The crops, livestock, fisheries and forestry subsectors of the Nigerian agricultural sector contributed 85%, 10%, 4% and 1%, respectively, to agricultural GDP. The crops and livestock subsectors have maintained their shares in recent years, while the fisheries sub-sector has been expanding and the forestry sub-sector shrinking. Given the large size of the crops sub-sector relative to the other three, growth performance in the crops sub-sector drives overall growth performance in agriculture. Among Nigeria's food staples, cereals account for the largest share of cultivated areas while roots and tubers account for the largest share of production due to their much higher yields per unit land area. Millet and sorghum, which are drought resistant crops, are grown in the northern part of Nigeria while the growth of maize and rice, which require more

moisture, are concentrated in the middle belts. Yam and cassava are grown extensively in the humid southern part of the country.

Food crop production in Nigeria has been driven entirely by expansion in area planted rather than by increase in productivity. Crop land expansion is increasingly taking place on marginal land where yields are lower. With the reduction of unused crop land, the current agricultural growth strategy, based on expansion of land area planted, becomes clearly unsustainable over the longer term. In the Nigerian agricultural sector, the major crops grown in the country are cowpea, sesame, cashew nuts, cassava, cocoa beans, groundnuts, gum arabic, kola nut, maize (corn), melon, millet, palm kernels, palm oil, plantains, rice, rubber, sorghum, soybeans and yams. These crops have commercial potentials of boosting the economy if mechanized through the use of modern techniques and equipment (Kasali, 2018).

Objective of Study

The main objective of this study is to identify the problems facing agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria and proffer several ways forward in overcoming these problems.

Agricultural Mechanization Practice

Agricultural mechanization involves the replacement of human and animal power with mechanical power. This covers the areas of land preparation, planting, livestock rearing and processing. According to Simalenga (2000), agricultural mechanization embraces manufacture, distribution and operation of all types of tools, implements, machines and equipment for agricultural land development, farm production, crop harvesting and primary processing. The definition of mechanization from the view of Akinbamowo (2013), however, is in contrast to the concept of many who erroneously take mechanization to mean the application of engineering principles to crop production only.

Farm mechanization has been seen as the pivot to the agricultural revolution in many parts of the world and has contributed remarkably by increasing the output of food crops and other agricultural products in meeting the demands of the ever increasing world population (Akande, 2009). Whereas FAO (1996) defined agricultural mechanization as a sector of the economy that embraces the manufacture, distribution and operation of all types of tools, implements, machines and equipment for agricultural land development, farm crop production, crop harvesting and primary processing.

Problems facing Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria

At the moment, there are some agricultural mechanization problems facing Nigeria which include fragmentation of farmlands or small landholdings due to land tenure system, poor capital base; non-access to credit; non setting up of manufacturing and repair services by entrepreneurs; no improved infrastructure; non affordable and secure access to complementary inputs (fuel, electricity and larger consolidated plot of land); worst legal and regulatory capacity to protect the right of owners of machinery; lower efficiency and capacity of public sector for implementing agricultural policy objectives of the government; and insecurity.

Lands in many communities are inherited and an outright sale is forbidden. Communal lands are not sold to the investors who are looking for large portion of land to start their farm business. This is because many farmers have small holding which are scattered in different locations in the village, proceeds from these small land holdings will not meet the expenses on machinery and other inputs. The land fragments with numerous canals and drainage ditches, narrow access road to individual plots restricts the use of mechanized equipment (El-Hossary, 1988).

Olatide et al. (1980) observed that about ninety percent of farmers (peasants ones) operate in subsistent level. This makes them to have no capital to invest in their farm lands, and at harvest period, they sell their farm produce and make use of the money without ploughing it back into agriculture. This on the other hand affects their next planting season. Many of them also have no collateral for credit facilities. They cannot even come together to form cooperative and put their resources to investment. It also makes them not to have access to credit facilities from commercial houses or the government. It is due to lack of money that the farmers cannot protect their machinery and buy some complementary inputs.

The government owned tractors and implements have limited or no trained personnel to repair and maintain them. To worsen the situation, hiring was bureaucratically bottlenecked due to the processes involved. The level of agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria is very low. This is in agreement with the study carried out by Oyelade et al. (2019) during a survey exercise conducted by NCAM where it is reported that nearly all the unit operations (peeling, washing, chipping, garification and bagging) carried out in the 116 cassava processing centres visited in Ekiti State are manually done with little or no involvement of mechanical device. It was only in the case of grating, dewatering and milling unit operation of cassava that they had larger extent of mechanical involvement than manual involvement.

Role Played By the Three Tiers of Government in Overcoming the Problems Facing Agricultural Mechanization Practice in Nigeria

Several policies in agriculture have been formulated by government with various set objectives as enumerated by FMA (1989) which include (i) production of food to meet the population growth; (ii) production of raw material for local agro-industries and for export to earn foreign exchange; and (iii) improvement and protection of agricultural land resources and preservation of the environment for sustainable agricultural production. According to Akinbamowo (2013), the Nigerian Federal constitution has divided responsibility for agricultural development among the three tiers of government and these are contained in the exclusive and concurrent legislative lists. The Federal Government's roles are mainly in three forms, namely developmental roles, supportive roles and service delivery roles. Of interest are those policies that have direct effect on mechanization.

Roles played by individual Tiers of Government **Federal Government**

The roles played by the Federal Government in the area of demand-driven agricultural research and biotechnology in continually increasing crop yield as reported by Akinbamowo (2013) include:

- i. Giving support to rural infrastructural development;
- ii. Developing and maintaining large dams and their auxiliary infrastructure for irrigation and also providing support to the State and Local Governments to do same to the smaller dams;
- iii. Maintaining the Strategic National Food Reserve for food security purpose; and
- iv. Promoting agro-industrial development.

State Governments

According to Akinbamowo (2013), the roles played by the State Governments include:

- i. Promoting primary production of all items of agricultural produce;
- ii. Development and management of the irrigation areas of large dams;
- iii. Management of impounded water and downstream structure of large dam;
- iv. Promoting appropriate farm mechanization;
- v. Investing in rural roads and water supply; and
- vi. Training and manpower development.

Local Governments

The roles played by the Local Governments, according to Akinbamowo (2013), include:

- i. Provide rural infrastructure;
- ii. Manage the irrigated areas of the dams;
- iii. Provide land for farming activities within the provision of Land Use Act.

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According to FMA (2001), a critical appraisal of the performance of the mandate of the three tiers of government in previous development plans reveals the existence of role duplication and overlapping of functions. Efforts have been made in the subsequent National Policy adopted in October, 2001 to re-define roles and remove such functional muddles to enhance efficiency.

Implementation Strategies

Reports provided by FMA (1984, 1989, 2002), comprehensively discussed the various strategies that have been adopted by government in implementing mechanization policies. These include:

- i. Supervision, monitoring and subsidizing agricultural land clearing by the State Government;
- ii. Establishment of tractor hiring unit (THU) and repair workshop by State Governments to encourage mechanized farming by peasant farmers. The ultimate goal is to promote privatizing THU's in assisting entrepreneurs in securing capital for private mechanization enterprises;
- iii. Introducing low horsepower and low cost 4-wheeled tractor;
- iv. Equipment fabrication and distribution at subsidized rate. This includes their standardization by specialized institution like the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM);
- v. Promoting animal traction and development of appropriate hand tools for agricultural production;
- vi. Strengthening existing institutions and encouraging private sector to invest in farm tools and equipment fabrication and marketing;
- vii. Development of simple processing and storage technologies for agricultural produce to reduce post-harvest losses;
- viii. Provision of necessary infrastructure to the rural areas through the national policy on integrated rural development to attract private sector;
- ix. Promote existing agro-processing facilities available in the country by enlightening small investors with the potential economic opportunities that exist in the simple cottage agro-processing activities;
- x. Provision of water from reservoirs and lakes for irrigation purpose to farmers and other groups of people as well as for urban water supply schemes;
- xi. Providing a comprehensive development of both underground and surface water resources for multi-purpose use.
- xii. Retention of all existing agencies for water resources development and exploitation such as the River Basin Development Authorities, State Water Boards, etc. and streamlining their operation to make them efficient and effective;

- xiii. Provision of adequate funds and support for the existing Rural Agro-industrial Development Scheme (RAIDS) to undertake more research into low cost and adoptive small- scale agro-processing machines; and
- xiv. Rehabilitation of farm machinery.

In implementing these policies on agriculture, government set-up various programmes or agencies mandated with the execution of specific components of its agricultural development policies. FMA (1984, 1989, 2002) listed such institutions to include:

1. Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) which was a programme aimed at mobilizing the general populace and creating an increased awareness for agricultural pursuit.
2. Green Revolution was a programme designed to effectively implement the objectives of Operation Feed the Nation (OFN).
3. Agricultural Development Projects (ADP) which was jointly funded by the World Bank, the Federal Government and the State Government was established with the main objective to promote integrated rural development by providing facilities for intensive agricultural extension services, modern input and distribution system, and rural infrastructure, especially rural feeder roads.
4. National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) was a programme meant to increase the production of grains and cassava through enhanced farm productivity brought about by adequate supply of improved input packages and crop processing and storage facilities.
5. Agricultural Development Authority (ADA) was like a complementary programme to ADP which was designed to reach out to the people at the grass root. That is, those area not covered by the ADP such as the Local Government Area (LGA).
6. River Basin Development Authorities has eleven of its Authorities created through Decree No. 87 of 1979. Initially, their activities cut across most area of agricultural development but the mandate was later reduced to cover only water resource development/maintenance of irrigation, dams etc.
7. The Federal Ministry of Agriculture created some parastatals such as the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM); National Grain Production Company; National Root Crops Production Company; and Nigerian Beverages Production Company.
8. Specialized institutions such as Universities of Technology, Universities of Agriculture and Colleges of Agriculture were also created.

Research institutes were to be coordinated by Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria (ARCN).

Assessment of these formulated Policies

The assessment of some extant policies as carried out by Ogboru (2002) noted that apart from the different funding agencies, the objectives of the programmes were more or less the same; self-sufficiency in agricultural production. The inputs were basically the same; improved seedlings and chemicals, fertilizers, machinery, extension service and training as well as credit. Many of the projects are deviations from extant policies. Reviewing the performance of the agricultural sector, Idachaba (1989) reported lack of functional integration between Ministries of Agriculture at State and Federal levels, and also lack of horizontal integration and definition of appropriate roles between line ministries at the Federal level leading to institutional ambiguity and role confusion. He further noted that joint Federal – State programmes have often favoured the creation of semi-autonomous project management units outside the mainstream i.e. Ministry of Agriculture.

Grandval and Mathilde (2011) in their review, remarked these policies as opportunistic, uncoordinated without plans for continuity such that successes, failures and lessons learnt in preceding programmes have not been analyzed. They noted for instance that subsidy for inputs has been a central element of Nigeria agricultural policy since 1950, however the application of subsidies have followed a spiky path with highs and lows and variable methods of implementation from 10% to 50% between Federal and State Governments. Even with this, many farmers still find it difficult to get inputs as at when needed due to poor regulation and monitoring to prevent diversion outside the country. Furthermore, Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe (2012) identified nine gaps in the development of national agricultural policy top among them is that these policies have no specific objectives, strategy, targets and most importantly programmes or projects geared towards accomplishment of the goals. Sometimes, agricultural programmes/projects are not consequences of agricultural policies.

Other gaps identified are non-interaction between and among stakeholders, role conflict between different programmes and projects, short duration of agricultural policies and programmes, incompatibility of regional policies/programmes with the national policies/programmes, emphasis on mainly food and animal production, inadequate virile technical advisory/extension services, inadequate monitoring and evaluation of programme/project as well as delay, embezzlement, misappropriation and lack of fund to pursue specific programme to an expected end.

Constraints to the Achievement of these created Policy Objectives

FMA (2001) identified some fundamental weaknesses that impede the effectiveness of agricultural mechanization policies and programme implementation, which include:

1. Hostile environment where macroeconomic policies and the agricultural policy are in disharmony thus resulting in escalating costs of production and reduced purchasing power of farmers.
2. Inconsistency and instability in macroeconomic policies which discourage medium and long term investments in agriculture.
3. Poor state of rural infrastructure.
4. Lack of appropriate indigenous technology to reduce the drudgery in agricultural production and processing activities.
5. Inadequate technology.
6. Inadequate database for policy formulations, monitoring and evaluation as well as impact assessment.
7. Poor translation and articulation of policy prescription into implementable programme.
8. Lack of involvement of beneficiaries in programme designs monitoring and evolution and implementations arising from under-rating of the knowledge, ability, capability and sensitivity of the small scale farmers.
9. Lag between project costs and budgetary provision resulting in sub-optimal allocation.
10. Fragmentation of farmlands into small unit which is sometimes far apart.
11. Cropping systems not often adequate for mechanizations.

Recently Created Agricultural Policies/Programmes

Agricultural Transformation Agenda Support Programme - Phase 1

The Federal Government has instituted the national economic transformation Agenda whose aim is to diversify the economy from reliance on oil, assure food security and create jobs, especially for the youth. In line with this, the Federal Ministry of Agricultural and Rural Development had implemented an Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) that will promote agribusiness, attract private sector investment in agriculture, reduce post-harvest losses, add value to local agricultural produce, develop rural infrastructure and enhance access of farmers to financial service and markets. ATA was set out to create over 3.5 million jobs along the value chains of the priority crops of rice, sorghum, cassava, horticulture, cotton, cocoa, oil palm, livestock, fisheries, etc for Nigeria's teeming youths and women, in particular ATASP-1 (2013).

Anchor Borrowers Programme

The Anchor Borrowers Programme initiative was launched by President Muhammadu Buhari in November 2015 to boost agricultural production, improve foreign exchange and reverse Nigeria's negative balance of trade on food. Smallholder farmers cultivating cereals (rice, maize, wheat etc.) cotton, roots and tubers, sugarcane, tree crops, legumes, tomato and livestock are those captured under the initiative. Loans are disbursed to the beneficiary farmers through Deposit Money Banks (DMBs), Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) and Microfinance Banks (MFBs), which the programme recognises as Participating Financial Institutions (PFIs). According to the guidelines of the programme, upon harvest, the farmer repays their loans by taking their harvest to 'anchors' who pay the cash equivalent to the farmer's account (www.premiumtimesng.com/news/506666-anchor-borrowers-programme-over-4.8-million-farmers-financed-buhari.html).

President Muhammadu Buhari recently said in the early month of year 2022 that the Anchor Borrowers Programme initiative launched six years ago had supported over 4.8 million smallholder farmers across Nigeria to boost production of 23 agricultural commodities in the country. This statement of President Muhammadu Buhari was given while unveiling stacked paddy rice pyramids produced by rice farmers under the Anchor Borrowers Programme initiative across the country. Presently, rice production in the country has increased to over 7.5 million metric tonnes annually (www.premiumtimesng.com/news/506666-anchor-borrowers-programme-over-4.8-million-farmers-financed-buhari.html).

Green Alternative

The Green Alternative was indeed the outcome of the discussion that emanated from the Agriculture Promotion Policy 2016 - 2020 document. The discussion involved multiple stakeholders who started discussing right from November 2015 to April 2016 before arriving at the Green Alternative. Building on the successes and lessons learnt from ATA, the vision of the Buhari Administration for agriculture was to work with key stakeholders to build an agribusiness economy capable of delivering sustained prosperity by meeting domestic food security goals, generating exports, and supporting sustainable income and job growth. This new policy regime tagged Agriculture Promotion Policy (APP) which ran from 2016 to 2020 was founded on the following guiding principles, a number of which were carryovers from ATA reflecting the strong desire for policy stability.

New elements added reflect the lessons from ATA, as well as priorities emerging from the aspirants of the Buhari Administration to include agriculture as a business; agriculture as key to long-term economic growth and security; food as a human right; value chain approach; prioritizing crops; market orientation; factoring climate change

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and environmental sustainability; participation and inclusiveness, policy integrity; nutrition sensitive agriculture; and agriculture's linkages with other sectors. Within this overall set of policy principles, the Federal Government provided an enabling environment for stakeholders at Federal and State level to play their distinctive roles. This policy emphasized on providing a conducive legislative and agricultural knowledge framework, macro policies, security enhancing physical infrastructure and institutional mechanisms for coordination and enhancing access to adequate inputs, finance, information on innovation, agricultural services and markets (www.fmard.gov.ng/green-alternative/).

Green Imperative

Many African countries face challenges in accessing cutting-edge technology, which can be seen in the difficulty of the agriculture sector in integrating into global networks. African agriculture, led by smallholder farmers, has yet to be assimilated into digital fluxes, a solution that hinders the use of new applications and services to boost productivity. Nigeria is the top African economy in terms of GDP, regional disparities are evident, and its rural spaces are still suffering with poor infrastructure and low levels of mechanization, making connections between suppliers, producers, distributors and consumers extremely difficult (www.my.southsouth-galaxy.org/en/solutions/detail/brazil-nigeria-green-imperative).

In view of this, the Green Imperative project which was launched by His Excellency, Prof. Yemi Osinbajo, Vice President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in 2019 champions the use of Brazilian technology for the development of agricultural mechanization to make farming a dignified venture for Nigerian people and, ultimately, increase agricultural production and boost food security. The solution for Nigeria is the connection of the agricultural value chain through an investment package of over \$1 billion (initial financing), has been set by the Governments of Brazil and Nigeria for improving the overall infrastructure in rural areas of Nigeria. The Green Imperative in partnership with some Brazilian agencies, the Nigerian government is focused on the construction of power plants, training structures and agro-processing factories, with a special interest in the acquisition of rural machinery such as tractors, drillers, seeders, cultivators, harvesters, etc. The programme which has a duration of 10 years, the project will have two phases of implementation (a) allocation of over \$200 million for the creation of around 780 agricultural service centres as the poles for catalyzing through training and equipment-sharing, the increase in productivity, and (b) technology transfer from Brazil to Nigeria via the commercialization of agricultural equipment and inputs, such as tractors, planters, seeders, fertilizers and pesticides (www.my.southsouth-galaxy.org/en/solutions/detail/brazil-nigeria-green-imperative).

In terms of results, the Green Imperative is still in the early stage of its implementation, and despite the large size of the project, results achieved to date have been small. With the execution of its first phase, the construction of 30 agricultural service centres in the most sensible rural areas serve as a pilot for the assessment of impacts and evaluation of risks, adapting the technical training to the specific demands of each location. The Brazil-Nigeria cooperation scheme is set to benefit over 100,000 young Nigerian professionals directly and more than 5 million Nigerian people indirectly, the transfer of technology, on the other hand, is set to involve the trade of 50,000 machines and equipment and 10,000 tractors which will be assembled by professionals in Nigeria (www.my.southsouth-galaxy.org/en/solutions/detail/brazil-nigeria-green-imperative).

Ways Forward and Conclusion

Ways Forward

Nigeria in her wake of doing so much in trying to diversify the nation's economy to agriculture as one of the best ways to rescue the present economic situation of the country from total collapse made it necessary for proposing the following way forward in overcoming the problems militating against the progress of agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria:

1. All past and new policies created by government on agricultural development that are still active till date should be reviewed to identify areas of duplication of function and seek for a way to resolve them.
2. The government either at the Federal or State levels should allow each formulated policy to end before reintroducing another one along the line which many at times is responsible for uplifting the same thing from ongoing policy thereby giving room for the duplication of function.
3. The land use decree of 1978 should be revised by government as this will decrease land fragmentation which at the long run will enable our farmers to acquire more land to support mechanized and commercial agriculture.
4. Policies created by government should be richly translated for effective implementation of the programme therein.
5. Policies created by government should be backed up with sufficient money to make them workable and lasting. This will solve the problem of policy implementation.
6. The three tiers of government should give room for continuity in policy statement so that it would not terminate such a good policy when a new government comes in.
7. Government should provide an enabling environment that will make agriculture a lucrative business in the face of farmers.

8. The Federal Government should provide all means of creating a strong synergy in form of functional integration between her own Ministry of Agriculture and that of the State Ministry of Agriculture in ensuring the success of agricultural development in Nigeria.
9. The practice of our cropping system in Nigeria should be designed in such a way that they are made adequate for mechanization.
10. All weaknesses found in both past and new policies of government should be carefully addressed.
11. The Federal Government should encourage Money Deposit Banks to lend to the agricultural sector. This can possibly work well if government can de-risk the agricultural sector by finding means of guaranteeing all loans borrowed by bank beneficiaries towards promoting agricultural productivity in Nigeria.
12. The Federal Government should strengthen the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) through the appropriation of more funds in order to fully discharge the mandate of the Centre.
13. Government needs to engage more agricultural extension officers in educating our farmers on the use of modern equipment.
14. Government should make fund available in training both engineers and technicians abroad on how to operate and maintain sophisticated farm machines. This training opportunity will ensure the continuous use of such machineries in the country.
15. Government needs to improve in the provision of infrastructural facilities such as good road network, constant electricity supply, good irrigation facilities, good storage facilities and good processing facilities. All these would encourage commercial farming and reduce postharvest losses.
16. There is need to identify the mandate of each agricultural agency of government so as to make good advantage of their usefulness in promoting agricultural development in Nigeria.
17. The Federal Government should formulate a policy on agricultural mechanization that will address all issues militating against agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria.
18. The Federal Government should look into the security situation of the country by guaranteeing farmers full safety on the farm site. This security situation in Nigeria at the moment might even make the country lose lots of investors (home and abroad) willing to invest their hard earned money on agriculture in Nigeria.
19. The low level of mechanization in Nigeria can be addressed if government can provide a soft loan for farmers that will be paid back in five years' time. This loan can go a long way in helping farmers to purchase the needed indigenously built agricultural machineries, implements, tools and

equipment in boosting agricultural productivity in Nigeria. This soft loan can come in form of a scheme as done in the case of so many small and medium scale enterprises where government used such scheme to boost their businesses.

20. The Federal Government should encourage the creation of tractor manufacturing plants in Nigeria which will provide the avenue for manufacturing tractors and its associated implements at a very cheap price that farmers and other end-users can afford to buy.

Conclusion

This paper has provided some way forward in overcoming the problems militating against agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria. Although, the agricultural sector had been neglected for long due to the emergence of oil which became the major revenue for running the country's economy over the past years. Now that the present administration of Buhari-Osinbajo led government had shown willingness and deep interest in diversifying Nigeria's economy to agriculture, it became important to make good use of the opportunity by supporting government's drive towards this direction. That is why all the aforementioned are presented in solving all the problems of agricultural mechanization practice in Nigeria.

References

- Akande, L. O. (2009). Effects of Agricultural Mechanization on Environmental Management in Nigeria: An Overview. *J. Pure Sci. Sci. Edu.*, 4 (2): 101 - 118.
- Akinbamowo, R. O. (2013). A Review of Government Policy on Agricultural Mechanization in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development*. Vol 5 (8):146-153.
- ATASP-1 (2013). Agricultural Transformation Agenda Support Programme - Phase 1: Strategic Environmental and Social Assessment (SESA) - Summary.
- El.Hossary, O. (1988). Mechanized Rice Production in Small Holdings, the Egyptian Experience. Proceedings of C. I. G. R. Inter-Sections Symposium / Nigerian Society of Agricultural Engineers held at the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, Ilorin, Nigeria; Sept. 5-10, 1988.
- FMA (1984). Information Bulletin on Nigerian Agriculture. Federal Ministry of Agriculture Publications. Lagos, 1984 FMA (1989) Agricultural policy for Nigeria.

Federal Ministry of Agriculture water Resources and Rural Development, Lagos Reprint.

FMA (1989) Agricultural policy for Nigeria. Federal Ministry of Agriculture water Resources and Rural Development, Lagos Reprint.

FMA (2001). New Agricultural Policy bulleting of the federal Ministry and Rural Development, Abuja.

FMA (2002). New Agricultural policy for Nigeria: Strategies for Implementation. Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development Publication, Abuja.

FAO (1996). Declaration on World Food Security. World Food Summit, November 13-17 (FAO) Rome.

Grandval, F. and D. Mathilde (2011). Nigeria's agricultural Policy, seeking coherence within strategic frameworks.

Idachaba, F. S. (1989). State - Federal Relations in Nigeria Agriculture. Madia Discussion paper 8. The World Bank, Washington D.C. P. 34.

Iwuchukwu, J. C and E. M. Igbokwe (2012) Lessons from Agricultural Policies and Programmes in Nigeria. J. Law, Policy and Globalization. ISSN 2224-3259 (Online). P. 5, 2012. www.iiste.org

Kasali, M. Y. (2018). Present Status and Future Prospects of Agricultural Machinery Research Activities in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Mechanization in Asia, Africa and Latin America*. 49(2): 135 - 149.

Ogboru I (2002). Agricultural Development Policies in Nigeria: A critique. Jos J. Econ. 2:1-9.

Olatide, O. J., Emeka, A., Bello Osagie VE. (1980). Nigerian Small farmers: Problems and Prospects in Integrated Rural Development. CARD. Univ. Ibadan, Nigeria. Pp.18-155

Oyelade, O. A., Y. S. Ademiluyi and B. L. Bamidele (2019). Present Status of the Level of Agricultural Mechanization available for Cassava Processing Operations in Ekiti State of Nigeria. *Continental J. Sustainable Development*. 10 (1): 14 - 21. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3345078.

Simalenga, T. E. (2000). Entrepreneurship in Mechanized Agriculture Technology-Oriented Operations. Agric. Mech. J. (AMA) 31(3):61-68.

www.premiumtimesng.com/news/506666-anchor-borrowers-programme-over-4.8-million-farmers-financed-buhari.html.

www.fmard.gov.ng/green-alternative/

www.my.south-galaxy.org/en/solutions/detail/brazil-nigeria-green-imperative.